

PREVENTION OF VIOLENCE AGAINST CHILDREN: FOREIGN EXPERIENCES AND SCIENTIFIC ANALYSES

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Abstract: In this article, the author analyzes foreign experiences and scientific views of legal scholars regarding the prevention of violence against children.

Keywords: Violence, physical force, parents, foreign experience, children.

According to WHO data, more than half of the world's children - that is, over 1 billion children - are subjected to violence every year. Key statistical indicators show that more than half of children aged 2 to 17 experience some form of violence annually (over 1 billion children), three out of five children are regularly punished with physical force at home, one in five girls and one in seven boys are subjected to sexual violence, and 25 to 50 percent of children become targets of bullies. Additionally, weapons and other forms of violence are a major cause of adolescent deaths.[1]

It is known that violence or cruelty against children is physical, sexual and/or psychological abuse of a child or group of children by a parent or caregiver, or neglect in general. Violence against children can include any act or omission by a parent or caregiver that results in actual or potential harm to the child, and this usually occurs at the child's home or in the places of organizations, schools, or communities where the child spends time.

The terms child abuse and child cruelty are often used interchangeably. Nevertheless, some researchers view the term child abuse as an umbrella term encompassing neglect, exploitation, and human trafficking.

From this point of view, the prevention of violence against children is one of the most pressing issues of society. To prevent violence against children, different countries have developed their own experience and legal framework, as well as effective methods. This article examines ways to improve the prevention of violence against children by analyzing foreign experience and the opinions of legal scholars.

Various forms of violence, including physical, psychological, and emotional violence, are widespread among children worldwide. Among the reasons for this are socio-economic conditions, cultural values, low understanding and respect for children's rights, as well as stress and conflicts in the family.

There are several successful models and strategies abroad aimed at reducing violence against children.

In particular, Scandinavian countries, especially Sweden, have advanced experience in the field of children's rights and their protection. In Sweden, a law prohibiting violence against children has been adopted since 1979[2]. This law provides for a complete ban on violence in the family and at school for children.

Sweden also has a well-developed system of children's rights education. There are special services for the protection of children's rights, their legal protection, and the fight against domestic violence. All this is effective in preventing violence.

Several large organizations and government agencies operate in the USA to prevent violence against children. For example, Child Protective Services (CPS) play an important role in protecting children's rights and identifying cases of domestic violence. An important factor in preventing violence against children in the USA is a comprehensive system of legal and psychological assistance. In addition to this, educational programs are actively implemented in schools and public organizations to prevent harm to children[3].

Germany has effective laws aimed at preventing violence against children. The "Jugendschutzgesetz" (Youth Protection Act) provides for the protection of children from domestic violence and the protection of their rights in the country. Germany has also established institutions that provide psychological support to protect children from psychological and physical abuse[4].

According to legal scholars [5], the following principles should be implemented in the prevention of violence against children:

The state's legal system plays a significant role in protecting children's rights. Countries need to adopt strict laws prohibiting violence against children. It is also important to strengthen special criminal liability for the protection of children and create a system for providing assistance to children who have experienced violence. Such a system should provide psychological, medical, and legal assistance.

Scientists emphasize the importance of preventing violence against children in the education system. Here, it is necessary to inform not only children, but also parents about the prevention of violence. For example, family education courses, psychological support services, and mass media that promote violence should be widely promoted.

Scientists also emphasize the need to involve society in the fight against violence. People should resist violence and be active in protecting children. This will help improve public attitudes towards children.

- Creating comprehensive laws: Every country needs to develop strong laws to protect children's rights. These laws should provide for a complete prohibition of physical, psychological, and emotional violence.

- Education and psychological support: Psychological and pedagogical methods for preventing violence should be implemented through educational programs in schools and society.

- Advocacy for parents and the public: It is necessary to conduct awareness campaigns for parents and the general public about the harmful consequences of violence.

- Creation of digital resources and data systems: Digital platforms and support systems should be created for children who have experienced violence.

In conclusion, it can be said that improving the prevention of violence against children is a complex and multifaceted issue that requires joint activity of all segments of society. Based on foreign experience, each state should approach this issue by creating effective systems for protecting children's rights, preventing violence, and educating society. The introduction of legal, pedagogical, and psychological assistance, as well as the involvement of the public in this process, is of great importance.

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